

PEECH SIGNAL CONTROL SOFTWARE IS AN IMPORTANT PART
OF OUR LIVES.

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Annotation: *This article introduces voice user interfaces to speech recognition programs, such as voice dialing, for example, "call home", call forwarding, for example, "I want to call", control of domicile devices, keyword search, for example, finding a podcast with specific words, entering simple data, for example, entering a credit card number, preparing structured documents, for example, radiology report, speaker features, speech-to-text processing, for example, word processors or electronic Mail messages and airplanes are usually called direct voice access.*

Keywords: *The power of speech sounds is the amount of energy that travels through a space of a certain width at a given time. This indicator affects the energy and power of speech. The timbre of speech sounds is formed by the main tone. This parameter is different for different people so this parameter is in human speech recognition systems*

In the formation of these sounds, different speech organs perform their functions on the basis of different formations. That is, which one vibrates or closes as needed. Speech pre-processing subsystem Speech signal pre-processing includes the following steps: - the process of access to the speech signal; - selection of the limit of the speech signal; - digital filtering; - Interrupting the speech signal with overlapping frames; - window signal processing; - spectral transformation; - frequency spectrum normalization. Audio input is done in real time via WAV files encoded on the sound card or PCM. 8 kHz sampling rate and 16-bit quantization are typical in speech data transmission, storage and processing systems

parameters. Working with files has been introduced to facilitate multiple repetitions of neural network processing, which is especially important for training. Separation of speech signals The following features of a speech signal are used to separate sections containing only speech from the input signal: • short-term energy of the speech signal; • number of intensity zeros (instantaneous frequency); • Distribution density of pause

report value. The transient energy and intensity zeros of the audio signal are used to output speech from the input signal at the same time. You can also remove the waste pause using the Gaussian distribution method.

Digital filtering Usually different sounds are accompanied by a useful signal. Noise negatively affects the quality of speech recognition systems, so it must be combated. Two types of digital filters are used to reduce the noise level in a small system:

- a conductive filter;
- Pre-filtering

Information about the amplitude of the speech signal and the shape of the envelope is insufficient to separate lexical elements from the speech. Depending on different conditions, the envelope shape of the speech signal can vary widely. To solve the recognition problem, it is necessary to select the basic speech features used in the later stages of the recognition process. Primary features are determined by analyzing the spectral properties of the speech signal. Information about the amplitude of the speech signal and the shape of the envelope is not sufficient to distinguish lexical elements from speech. Depending on different conditions, the envelope shape of the speech signal can vary widely. To solve the recognition problem, it is necessary to select the basic speech features used in the later stages of the recognition process. Primary features are determined by analyzing the spectral properties of the speech signal. Spectral analysis of the speech signal

In processing systems, the analog speech signal is transmitted to the input of the microphone, from which an electrical signal is obtained. Then the signal is sampled in time and the amplitude is quantified

Speech detection This interdisciplinary subfield Computer science and computational linguistics develops methodologies and technologies that allow recognition and translation of spoken language into text by computers. Also known as automatic speech detection (ASR), computer speech detection or text speech (STT). It includes knowledge and research in the fields of computer science, linguistics, and computer engineering. Some systems for speech recognition require a "report" (also called a "record"), where A separate speaker reads the text or isolates the dictionary system. The system analyzes a person's specific voice and uses it in precise tuning to recognize that person's speech, resulting in increased accuracy. Systems that do not use training are called "speaker independent" [1] systems. Systems that use training are called "speaker dependent".

Speech recognition programs include voice user interfaces, such as voice dialing (e.g., "call home"), call forwarding (e.g., "I want to call"), and domain tools. management, keyword search (e.g., finding a podcast where specific words are spoken), entering simple information (e.g., entering a

credit card number), preparing structured documents (e.g., radiology report), identifying speaker features, [2] word-to-word processing of speech (e.g., word processors or emails and aircraft is usually referred to as direct voice input. Additional voice recognition [3] [4] [5] or speaker ID [6] [7] [8] refers to the identification of the speaker, not the speakers. or confirmation can be used for cooling.

possible.

By the early 2010s, speech recognition was clearly different from recognition, also known as voice recognition. [54] [55] [56] Speaker recognition and speaker independence were considered major achievements. Until then, the systems required a "training" period. The 1987 ad for the doll had a caption that read, "Finally, a doll that understands you." - despite being described as "which children can be taught to respond to their own voices." [12]

In 2017, Microsoft researchers reached a historic humane stage in transcribing conversational telephony speech into the widely used Switchboard function. Several in-depth study models have been used to optimize the accuracy of speech detection. Speech recognition error rates were reported to be as low as 4 professional human transcribers working together on the same indicator, funded by the IBM Watson speech team in the same task. Both acoustic modeling and language modeling important parts of modern statistical-based speech detection algorithms. Hidden Markov models (HMM) are widely used in many systems. Language modeling is also used in many other natural language processing programs Classification of documents or statistical machine translation

gives probability for the vector. Each word, or (for general speech recognition systems), each has a phoneme, a different output distribution; the hidden Markov model for a sequence of words or phonemes is accomplished by combining hidden Markov models trained for individual words and phonemes.

The key elements of the most common HMM-based approach in speech recognition described above. Modern speech recognition systems use various combinations of a number of standard methods to improve the results of the basic approach described above. Usually a large vocabulary system is needed for context-dependent phonemes (so different left and right contextual phonemes have different concepts for HMM cases); it uses cepstral normalization to normalize for different speaker and recording conditions; To normalize the speaker it is possible to use the normalization of the length of the vocal tract for the normalization of the male-female to

adjust the overall speaker of the maximum probability linear regression. Features would be called delta and delta-delta coefficients to obtain speech dynamics and can also be used heterocedastic linear discriminant analysis or can skip and use delta-delta coefficients after attachment and based projection, possibly heterocedastic linear discriminant analysis or conversion of a global semi-linked co-operation (as well as the maximum probability of linear conversion to MLLT). Many systems use discriminatory teaching methods that abandon an absolutely statistical approach to assessing HMM parameters and instead optimize measurements related to certain classifications of learning data. Examples are maximum reciprocal information (MMI), minimum classification error (MCE), and minimum telephone error. Speech decoding term), perhaps to find the best way for the Viterbi algorithm, and here there is a choice between creating a hidden Markov model that dynamically contains acoustic and language model data and combining it pre-statically, or approach) .Possible improvement in decoding is the evaluation of these good candidates so that we can choose the best one according to that particular candidate instead of retaining the best candidate and using the higher score function. Candidate package can be stored as a list approach) or as part of models. Re-scoring is usually done by trying to minimize (or approach) it: Instead of accepting the first sentence with maximum probability, we try to obtain a sentence that minimizes the expectation of a given loss function on all possible transcriptions (i.e. we obtain a statement that minimizes the average distance) to other possible judgments drawn with an approximate probability). Loss function

Dynamic change of time is a historically used approach to speech recognition, but is now largely due to a more successful HMM-based approach. Dynamic change of time can vary in time or speed An algorithm for measuring the similarity between two sequences. For example, similarities in walking style can be detected even if a person is walking slowly in one video and walking faster in another, or if there is acceleration and deceleration during one observation. DTW applies to video, audio, and graphics - any data that can actually be converted to a line image can be analyzed using DTW.The popular program is automatic speech recognition to overcome different speech speeds. In general, this is a method that allows a computer to find the optimal fit between two sequences (e.g., time series) given with certain constraints. That is, the sequences are "linear" that correspond to each other. This sequence alignment method is often used in the context of latent Markov models.

lish. When used to predict the probability of a speech feature segment, neural networks allow for natural and effective discriminatory training. However, despite their effectiveness in classifying short time units such as individual phonemes and individual words, [63] early neural networks have rarely been successful for continuous recognition tasks due to their limited ability to model temporal connections. one is the use of neural networks as pre-processing, modification of properties, or reduction in size ed [step before recognition on the basis of HMM. However, recently LSTM and similar repetitive neural networks and time-delayed neural networks have demonstrated improved performance in this area. Deep neural networks and denoising Autoencoders [68] are also under investigation. A deep neural network (DNN) is an artificial neural network with several latent layers of units between the input and output layers. [42] Similar to shallow neural networks, DNNs can model uncomplicated linear relationships. DNN architectures create composite models, here in addition ayers allow the compilation of features from lower layers, which provides greater learning ability and thus the ability to model complex patterns of speech data. [69] The success of DNNs in recognizing large lexical speech in 2010 where large output layers of DNN were adopted based on context-dependent HMM cases constructed on the basis of decision trees. [70] [71] [72] See full reviews of this development and modern level in October 2014 in Microsoft Research's latest Springer book. [73] Automatic speech recognition and the impact of various machine learning paradigms, in particular, see in-depth study, one of the basic principles of misinformation is in-depth study is the elimination of handcrafted feature engineering and the use of raw properties. This principle was first successfully studied in in-depth autocoder architecture on "raw" spectrogram or linear filter-bank properties, [76] showing its superiority over Mel-Cepstral properties by removing multiple variable changes from spectrograms. includes z. The real "raw" features of speech, the waveforms, have recently led to very large-scale speech detection results. [77] Since 2014, there has been a great deal of interest in the "end-to-end" ASR. Traditionally on a phonetic basis (i.e., all HMM-based model) approaches are separate components and pronunciation, acoustic, and language model. End-to-models together explore all the components of speech recognition. This is important because it simplifies the learning process and the distribution process. For example, a n-gram language model is required for all HMM-based systems, and typically an n-gram language model takes up a few gigabytes of memory, making it unwise to

place them on mobile devices. [78] Consequently, modern commercial ASR systems are hosted in the cloud by Google and Apple (as of 2017) and require a local network connection unlike a device. Direct study of all components of speech recognition, including pronunciation, acoustics, and language model possible. This means that there is no need to carry a language model, which is very practical for applications with limited memory during deployment. By the end of 2016, the models in focus had achieved significant success, including surpassing the CTC models (with or without an external language model). [86] Various extensions have been proposed since the original LAS model. Direct extraction of sub-word units proposed by Hidden Sequence Decompositions (LSD) and more natural than Google Brain English characters; [87] Oxford to manage above human level The LAS has been expanded to "Watch, Listen, Participate, and Spell" (WLAS). . After the voice command, the system has a "listening window" during which it can receive speech recognition. can be used to listen to music from a built-in flash drive. Voice recognition skills vary depending on the make and model of the vehicle. Some recent [when?] Car models offer speech recognition in natural language instead of a strict set of commands that allow the driver to use complete sentences and common phrases. With such systems, the user does not need to memorize fixed command words. Speech recognition from the front is when the provider instructs the speech recognition engine that the recognized words are displayed when they are spoken and the dictator is responsible for editing and signing the document. Backward or delayed speech recognition is a digital dictation system in which the provider assigns an "a", a voice speech recognition machine and the featured project document is edited to the editor along with the original audio file and the report is completed. Delayed speech detection is now widely used in the field. brings great financial benefits to physicians who use them in accordance with their standards. These standards require that large amounts of data be stored by EMR (now more commonly referred to as ".") (Electronic Health Records or EHR). The use of speech recognition is naturally more appropriate when creating a story text as part of a radiological / pathological interpretation, a development note or summary: ergonomic achievements of speech recognition to enter structured individual data (e.g., numerical values or codes)) register or a controlled dictionary) is relatively minimal for people who can see and can control the keyboard and mouse.

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